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THE IMPORTANCE OF BOOK TRAILER TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: This article explores the historical development stages of book trailer educational technology, reviews international experiences in applying book trailers within educational settings, and outlines the methods by which this technology is implemented across various countries' education systems.

Key words: educational technology, technological tools, mass media, multimedia learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada "book trailer" (kitob treyleri) ta'lim texnologiyasining tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari, uni ta'lim jarayonida qo'llashga doir xalqaro tajribalar va turli mamlakatlar ta'lim tizimlarida mazkur texnologiyani joriy etish usullari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim texnologiyasi, texnologik vositalar, ommaviy axborot vositalari, multimedia o'qitish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются этапы исторического развития образовательной технологии бук-трейлеров, анализируется зарубежный опыт их применения в учебном процессе, а также описываются способы внедрения данной технологии в системы образования разных стран.

Ключевые слова: образовательные технологии, технологические средства, средства массовой информации, мультимедийное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the system of continuous education, enhancing the quality of education, and ensuring its efficiency require not only material factors but also the development of independent learning within educational institutions. The higher education system plays a crucial role in creating the necessary conditions for improving the mechanisms of independent student work and enabling them to operate in accordance with modern requirements. Indeed, at the current stage of societal and scientific-technological progress, an analysis of the educational process, its content, forms, methods, and tools, as well as its impact on specialist training, reveals the necessity of a creative approach to education, which is determined by the following factors:

Firstly, socio-economic development demands a fundamental renewal of the education system, its methodology, and the technology of the learning process. In such conditions, the teacher's role involves creating pedagogical innovations, mastering advanced practices, and acquiring the skills to implement them. Consequently, this naturally necessitates the development of creative abilities in future educators.

Secondly, humanizing the content of education and searching for new organizational forms and technologies of teaching necessitate the introduction of innovations in education. One of the key conditions for implementing innovations in the educational process is the teacher's innovative preparedness, creativity, and active engagement in creative practices.

Thirdly, developing an active inclination among future teachers toward acquiring and implementing pedagogical innovations in practice highlights the social, pedagogical, and psychological relevance of this research problem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is evident that a creative approach to the educational process is essential for developing students' creative abilities, as it fosters skills that evolve through active interaction. This, in turn, necessitates an interactive learning environment, teaching conditions, and methods in higher education institutions. "Organizing independent learning requires not only an interest in a specific profession or field of activity but also the presence of aptitude for that activity." Since independent learning is directly linked to independent thinking, it is appropriate to provide its definition as well: "Independent thinking is a mental activity in which a person, relying on their knowledge and life experience, determines the goals and objectives of the problems they face and solves them independently using various methods, techniques, and tools within the limits of their intellectual capabilities."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Accordingly, our research focuses on enhancing the necessary pedagogical conditions for developing students' creative abilities through independent learning, which has gained significant relevance in recent years. This includes fostering a free and creative educational environment, improving the integration of teaching and learning activities in higher education institutions, and implementing an integrated pedagogical system to increase the effectiveness of the learning process.

One of the main challenges of modern education is developing an interest in reading among the younger generation. Reading is not only a means of acquiring culture but also a tool for shaping worldview, intellectual growth, learning, and essential life skills. Moreover, high-quality reading contributes to the personal development and competitiveness of a modern individual living in a complex informational and cultural society.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An important direction in improving education is the transition to new educational technologies, one of which is book trailer technology.

Book trailers (from the English book trailer) are short videos that tell a story about a book in a creative, artistic form. The purpose of such videos is to promote reading and attract attention to books using visual tools similar to movie trailers. The history of book trailers dates back to 2002. However, starting in 2005, with the rise of video hosting platforms such as YouTube and the growth of social media, the practice of creating book trailers became widespread. Today, in the United States and Europe, almost no book marketing campaign is complete without book trailers, which have evolved into an independent art form. There are even several annual awards recognizing achievements in this field.

The main stages of creating a book trailer include several important steps. First, selecting a book for promotion is essential, and the most important criterion is a genuine love for the book itself. Next comes creating a script, which involves developing the plot and carefully writing the text. This stage is often the most challenging, as the goal is to spark curiosity without revealing too much—especially if the trailer is based on a fictional story.

When focusing on the book's overall atmosphere, one must determine the tone and how to effectively convey it through visuals and sound. After the script is finalized, materials for the video sequence should be gathered. This can involve scanning book illustrations, sourcing relevant images online, or using original artwork. If the book has been adapted into a film, selected frames may be used cautiously to avoid shifting the focus to the movie rather than the book. The next step involves recording narration if it is part of the script; otherwise, appropriate background music should be chosen. For assembling the trailer, a video editing program must be selected. Windows Movie Maker is recommended for beginners due to its user-friendly interface and accessibility, as it comes pre-installed on many Windows computers. This software allows users to capture and process video files, create slideshows, add transitions and titles, incorporate sound, trim and join clips, and apply effects—although it supports only one audio track. Once editing is complete—cutting and combining clips, adding subtitles, transitions, effects, and audio—the final video is saved to the computer. The process concludes with sharing the trailer with friends or family, gathering their feedback, and making necessary adjustments. Since a book trailer serves as an advertisement aimed at the audience, their opinions are crucial in refining the final version and ensuring it effectively convinces viewers of the book's value.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of book trailer technology into the educational process offers significant pedagogical value. It enhances students' engagement, stimulates creativity, and supports the development of critical thinking and digital literacy skills. Book trailers not only make literature more accessible and appealing but also foster a deeper emotional connection with texts. As an innovative tool, they bridge traditional reading practices

with modern multimedia approaches, thereby enriching the overall learning experience and preparing students for the demands of the digital age.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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